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ROLE OF COMMUNICATION IN ADDRESSING GENDER SENSITIVITY IN INTEGRATED WATERSHED MANAGEMENT PROGRAMME.

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Abstract:

In spite of the development interventions by many international agencies, the performance of India on women empowerment and gender equality is very poor. The sex ratio in many states of India has dropped to fewer than 850 females per 1000 males. India is ranked 127 out of 187 countries on Gender Inequality Index as per the 2014 Global Human Development Report (UNDP HDI report-2014). According to United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) where development is not “engendered” it is “en-dangered”. However, across the levels of governance, there are still concerns about socio political participation of women due to deeply rooted inequalities, social stigma, patriarchy, male dominance and limited scope for women to venture out from the boundary of four walls. So keeping view of the above facts Odisha Watershed Development Mission (OWDM) in its project called Integrated Watershed Management Programme(IWMP) has tried its best to do some gender related intervention which has lead to the socio, political and economic empowerment of women in rural areas of Odisha.

Key Words: Gender, UNDP, OWDM, IWMP

Introduction

A gender aware project enables a transformative process in and outside of the organization. It recognizes the contribution of both men and women in development. Empowerment implies a situation whereby women and men take control over their lives. They set their own agendas, gain skills, increase self-confidence and develop self-reliance. In order to make the watershed projects gender sensitive, a proper communication on the understanding of the different roles men and women play in the community, their different needs and concerns should be taken into consideration. In this context Integrated Watershed Management Programme has been taken up for a study to know the process of gender integration in its project areas.

Gender is a social construct, which assigns to both males and females certain attitudes, roles and responsibilities resulting in different opportunities and behavior. It varies from place to place and over time and is perpetuated through the process of socialization. It shapes and determines the behavior, roles, expectations and entitlements of women and men in a particular society. Gender is not “Sex”. Gender is not “Women”.

Gender Differences have led to the following gaps worldwide,

- Of the world’s 1.3 billion poor, nearly 70% are women

- Women constitute half of the world's population, two-thirds of the world's illiterates. Of the world's one billion illiterate two thirds are women.**(The literacy rate of Orissa:72.87% Male:81.59%, Female:62.46% as per 2011 census Report)**
- Women perform two-thirds of the world's work, one-tenth of the world's income, owns one-hundredth of the world's property
- Women are often married at an early age and are blamed for giving birth to a female child
- Women have no easy access to health care facilities (48 out of 100 women suffer from nutritional deficiency, the incidence of anemia, MMR and female IMR is very high in Orissa, **Sex ratio in Orissa is 979 for each 1000 male which is below national average of 940 as per 2011 census. 972 women as against 1000 men in Orissa)**
- Not aware of her rights but very cautious about duties, No share in HH decision-making
- Between 75-80% of the world's 27 million refugees are women and children
- Only 24 women have been elected as heads of Government in the last century**(In 14th Orissa Legislative assembly: 07women/147men)**
- Rural women produce more than 55% of all food grown in developing countries
- HIV is increasingly affecting women. Today about 42% of the estimated cases are those of women
- 20 million unsafe abortions are performed every year resulting in the deaths of 70,000 women
- In recent years, there has been an alarming rise in atrocities against women in India. Every 26 minutes a woman is molested, every 34 minutes a rape takes place, every 42 minutes a sexual harassment incident occurs, every 43 minutes a woman is burnt to death over dowry.

Problem Statement (Gender Situation in the Project area)

The tragic plight of women in Orissa is alarming. They lack access and control over income, have little or no participation in the village forum (Palli Sabha), are not involved in decision making, receive unequal wages, and have lower access to information compared to men. Other dimensions of gender inequalities include early marriage, dowry torture, female foeticide, lack of access to formal education and high levels of drudgery. Most interestingly, developmental efforts in the areas have not been able to break the iron grip of gender discrimination since the approach has been focusing only on women without changing the mindset and attitudes of men. Women are yet to be considered as equal partners in the development process. Women's participation remains confined within the mandatory provisions of representation without a change in the terms of participation. Women's role in productive, reproductive and community works goes largely unacknowledged and it is called the triple burden for women. At the same time, lacks of access to information and knowledge on women specific schemes and programmes have doubled their misery. Absence of skill building training deters the women to get involved in Non Farm activities. Women's involvement in planning, monitoring and decision making in different community level forums is not visible. Women's participation is very low even during Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) and Micro-level Planning Process (MLP) .Only economic issues of women are addressed through self help groups though there are many social issues which are yet to be addressed at the community level such as health, education, sanitation, violence against women, wage and entitlement etc.

Objective:

- To enable the stake holders on concepts and issues related to gender in development so that they can understand, analyse and utilise gender dimensions in development process.
- To know about various communications strategy adopted to increase gender sensitivity.

Hypothesis/Assumption

- Effective Communication on Equal Gender Relations lead to success in development projects
- Better access to communication helps in reducing the wide gap between men and women

Methodology

- Personal Discussions
- Interviews
- Field visit & Case analysis exercises.

Sample Study/Process of Data Collection

- The research paper has tried to analyse the importance of communicating gender in watershed projects of Odisha Watershed Development Mission, and the key strategies adopted to increase gender sensitivity among its various stake holders.
- Literature survey is done to gather information from other projects and what has been done and what should be done to address gender sensitivity in development projects. Personal discussions and interviews taken of 50 number of employees of watershed mission including field staffs.

OWDM Strategies and Experiences

Recognizing these problems in addressing women's participation and empowerment, and for effective communication on Gender integration in project villages, Orissa Watershed Development Mission has tried to address these issues through the following strategies,

Training on Gender Sensitization: Gender Sensitization Training was organized both for the secondary and primary stake holders of the project. Training of Trainers (ToT) was organized at the state level to create pool of resource persons on gender. These trainings helped in changing attitude and mindset of both men and women

Gender balance in district level staffing: To promote gender balance in staffing, Watershed Management Team members (Women) have been appointed at the block level under various streams such as Social Development, Micro-enterprise, livelihoods, and Natural Resource Management.

Developing women leadership in watershed villages: 33% mandatory reservation in watershed committees gives a platform for women to be a part of village developmental planning. In some exemplary watersheds women representation is even beyond 33%. Women are actively participating in the decision-making process not only at the household level but also at the community level. They have become a part and parcel of village developmental planning. It has been found that women participation in the village meeting has witnessed an increasing trend. To validate, the women in watersheds are able to share the activities of the project, have information on the amount of funds received from OWDM, their utilization and contribution towards Watershed Development Fund (WDF) etc. Further, gender sensitization trainings have helped the rural community to understand the need for women's participation in the "Palli Sabha" and other meetings.

Identification of Gender issues through Micro Level Planning Process (MLP)

Gender issues, concerns and priorities are included in the micro level planning process and during Detailed Project Report Preparation. Various tools such as division of labor, Access and Control Matrix, Practical Gender Needs (PGN) and Strategic Gender Needs (SGN) are used to identify the gender gaps in the community and how to overcome them. Women's participation is ensured during those exercises for better role clarity and finding solution to this age old problem.

Involvement in Social Development Activities by Women Self Help Groups

Self Help Groups are motivated to involve in activities beyond thrift and credit in watersheds. In addition they are uniting and organizing themselves into federations and actively taking up social issues like anti-liquor campaign, anti-tobacco campaign, construction of village roads, cleanliness drive, total sanitation campaign, forest protection, women and child rights protection, eradication of social evils like child labor,

early marriage and dowry, donating land for construction of schools, literacy campaigns, sensitizing other women on RCH, HIV/AIDS/Family planning methods/institutional delivery etc. In this way they have become a catalyst for social transformation and the leaders are acting as change agents/role models in the villages.

A Social Development officer has been appointed in the state management team to provide strategic input on Social Development & Gender, capacity building and formulation of a gender friendly HR policy.

Effectiveness of Information & Communication on increased Gender Sensitivity

Proper information Dissemination and sensitization programmes on Gender helps in reducing gender disparity in project villages. For increasing gender sensitivity , good documentation ,research, collection of sex-disaggregated data ,producing useful resources, materials on gender, and disseminating it in project villages are given utmost priority in the mission. Further Continuous Learning, sharing best practices, discussions and dialogues and organizing Learning Consultation and Briefing (LCB) workshops are regular events in the OWDM.

OWDM has developed Strategic Networking on gender with various GO/NGO engaged in gender related activities in the state. Regular exchange of information through emails, discussion groups, bulletin boards, and internet web are done for raising visibility of organizations activities on Gender.

Activities on Communication to increase gender sensitivity in OWDM

- Training to Secondary & Primary Stake Holders on Gender Sensitivity, for changing attitude and mindset of both men and women.
- Specific training to active women on leadership development.
- Focus is given to involve more women in self help groups and promote groups among left outs women.
- Development and circulation of Information, Education & Communication (IEC) materials in local language for better understanding on gender.
- Celebration of important days (Women Empowerment Day on March 8th of every year).
- Exposure to other successful projects to see successful women entrepreneurship.
- Ensure participation of women during micro-level planning process.
- Specific activities are taken up to address practical(drinking water facility, sanitation, health) and strategic gender needs(involve in decision making, developing leadership quality, awareness on legal rights and entitlements, access and control over resources).

Impact of the communication on Gender

Women have been given preference in the recruitment process resulting in appointment of more women. Appointment of a Social Development Officer at the state office. Leaflets/Brochures/Resource Book on Gender developed and circulated among all the stake holders. All staffs have been informed about Gender friendly HR policy .Maternity leave benefits have been written into the contracts of new candidates appointed, and in renewal of contracts. Posters on prevention of sexual harassment have been displayed. A complaints committee has been set up to deal with cases of sexual harassment with majority of women members. 33% mandatory reservation of women in all watershed committees. The sensitization of primary stakeholders is being organised through Cluster Livelihoods Resource Center Networks (LRCN). Women are allowed to come with children in the trainings conducted by the Cluster Livelihood Resource Centers .The trainings for the secondary stake holders are organized at IMAGE and DRWA at the state level. It is important to learn that women's voice is heard in the planning process and sincere efforts are made to enable women to actively participate in meetings/discussions/village level trainings/ etc. Case studies related to success and failure of the gender intervention help in chalk out future course of action.

Output of Communication

As a part of the communication strategy in IWMP, Flip Books, posters, Trainer's Resource Book on Gender have been developed, published and circulated among the district and block level stake holders for better understanding and conceptual clarity on gender. Short Films in Oriya language on women empowerment have been made for community members, self help group members and Panchayati Raj Institution members. It would help them in enhancing their knowledge and motivate to work for the noble cause. Further case studies on successful women leaders and entrepreneurs are documented in the Jeebika News Letter which is published in every quarter. The newsletter is circulated in project villages of all the 26 IWMP districts of Odisha.

Key Findings/Recommendations

As change Agents working in development projects, we must

- Contribute Gender perspectives to decision-making processes (Policy Advocacy, Programme Planning, and Budgeting) and ensure that gender equality consideration is taken into account in discussion and decision-making.
- Promote and facilitate inter-agency dialogue/workshops/seminars on gender mainstreaming. More skill based trainings for women.
- Analyze and collect sex-disaggregated data, and disseminate information on gender analysis & gender mainstreaming practice to the stake holders.
- Network extensively with state Government departments (Women & Child Development, Panchayati Raj, Directorate of Research on women in Agriculture)/national/international organizations such as UNFPA, UNDP, and DFID working on Gender.
- Record and find mechanisms for addressing equity issues of both men and women for learning from programmatic & organizational good practices
- Establishment of Gender Task Force at district/block level.

Challenges/Limitations

However, the project could not fully address some of the basic gender concerns like construction of gender friendly toilets at the district offices. As most of the District offices are operating in the building of other Government departments or are operating in hired buildings it was difficult to construct toilets in those premises. This shows that while organizational commitment could enable significant changes in HR policies, some practical needs of women employees could not be addressed. Analyses of sex disaggregated data on investment and income is not done fully.

There was a conscious attempt to give joint 'pattas' of land (land ownership) in the names of landless people (women and men both) in districts like Nuapada, Bolangir and Kalahandi. Though the names of both husband and wife are being mentioned in the land records but efforts have not been made yet for making it mandatory in all the districts. At present OWDM in collaboration with Landesa is creating awareness on land rights of women in project villages of Mayurbhanj district. The project may recognize this success in due course and scale it up to the full project area and also in other projects, offering a 'good practice' example to other official and donor supported projects.

Scope for further research on Gender

In order to bring about gender equity in development projects, more and more communication output activities need to be done and projects should be gender sensitive. The study gives apt justification to the hypothesis formulated in the beginning that better access to communication helps in reducing the wide gap between men and women. The study also provides scope

for researchers who are interested to do research on gender related communication in development organizations.

Conclusion:

Bringing a change in the society related to gender is a slow process. It requires systematic and continuous efforts. Though the major concern of the project is to take up soil and water conservation measures and address the livelihoods of the people still women's equality and empowerment is taken on board as an important aspect of watershed management. Hence creation of an enabling environment with a gender sensitive communication strategy is very much essential for increased status of the women in the family as well as society. To sum up, "Achieving gender equality among both men and women require changes at many levels, including changes in attitudes, mindset, changes in institutions and legal frameworks and changes in political decision making structures".

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List of Abbreviations

UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
PRI	Panchayati Raj Institution
OWDM	Orissa Watershed Development Mission
IWMP	Integrated Watershed Management Programme
PRA	Participatory Rural Appraisal
MLP	Micro-level Planning
WMT	Watershed Management Team Members
ToT	Training of Trainers
SHG	Self Help Group
PGN	Practical Gender Need
SGN	Strategic Gender Need
WDF	Watershed Development Fund
RCH	Reproductive and Child health
HIV/AIDS	Human Immune Deficiency Virus/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome
UNFPA	United Nations Population Fund
DFID	Department for International Development
IEC	Information, Education, Communication
LANDESA	Name of a rural development institute working on land rights of women
HH	Household